

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ANOMALOUS UTERINE BLEEDING IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE LIVING IN KHOREZM REGION

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Currently, in Khorezm, every second woman is aged 40 years and older, life expectancy women on average is 72 years. The increase in life expectancy has led to the fact that the modern woman spends almost 1/3 of his life in the period of menopause. With changes in the age structure of the population, diseases of women of transitional age occupy a special place. Wherein one of the main problems of this period is menstrual dysfunction, clinically manifested acyclic uterine bleeding, oligomenorrhea, menorrhagia, metrorrhagia, or polymenorrhea.

It becomes clear that uterine bleeding the presence of morphological changes is incorrect to attribute to dysfunctional, despite the fact that in these conditions the function of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian system (HPAS) can also be impaired, but bleeding during this will be secondary. Therefore, uterine bleeding that occurs in perimenopause, in contrast to from adolescence and reproductive period, in most cases are secondary and occur against the background of already existing organic pathology of the endometrium (hyperplasia, polyps) and uterus (myomatous nodes, adenomyosis). Thus, it is quite justified to call uterine bleeding in perimenopause abnormal and highlight: cyclic abnormal uterine bleeding - menorrhagia and acyclic abnormal uterine bleeding - metrorrhagia, as well as their combination - menometrorrhagia.

Dysfunctional uterine bleeding can be defined as abnormal uterine bleeding without signs of organic genital or extragenital pathology.

The purpose of the study: to present the clinical and morphological characteristics of women in the perimenopausal period with abnormal uterine bleeding according to the results of a retrospective analysis of case histories from 2019 to 2023.

Material and research method: In the course of the work, a retrospective analysis of 700 case histories of women aged 40 to 55 years, received by urgent indications with abnormal uterine bleeding (AMB) in the gynecological department of perinatal center of Khorezm region from 2019 to 2023 year. At the same time, in 2019, 86 (12.3%) patients, in 2020- 129 (18.4%), in 2021 - 108 (15.4%), in 2022 - 137 (19.6%) and in 2023 - 240 (34.3%) patients. During statistical processing of the obtained results, we used the methods of descriptive (descriptive) statistics, which included an estimate of the arithmetic mean (M) and the mean error of the mean (m), the frequency of occurrence of features. To compare the frequency values, we used χ^2 - Pearson's criterion. We also used the methods of linear correlation analysis — Pearson's parametric test (r) and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (rs).

Results and its discussion: When studying the distribution of patients by years

from 2019 to 2023 age differences were revealed was not ($r_s = 0.05$; $p > 0.05$), which gives us reason to consider all those admitted to women's clinic (700 people) as a joint (homogeneous) group without taking into account the year of admission.

All patients were divided into 3 age groups: group 1 — 262 (37.4%) women aged 40 to 45 years, 2nd group — 321 (45.9%) patient aged 46 to 50 years and the 3rd group - 117 (16.7%) women aged 51 up to 55 years old. From the data presented, it follows that most often, women aged 46 to 50 years were admitted to the hospital with AUB ($\chi^2 = 17.84$; $p < 0.05$). At the same time, the average age of women with AUB was 46.7 ± 0.1 years.

Conclusions:

1. Most often (45.9%), AUB occurs in women aged 46 to 50 years (46.7 ± 0.1 years). However, patients do not report abnormalities, menstrual (87.4%) and reproductive functions (92.9%) in history.

2. In perimenopausal women with AUB, obesity is more common (26.5%) compared to with healthy women and progressively increases with age. Extragenital pathology is presented in almost half of the patients in the form of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (23.6%), cardiovascular system (16.3%) and genitourinary systems (13.1%). Iron-deficiency anemia was detected in 44.9% of admitted women.

3. Uterine fibroids are combined with AUB in 78.7% of perimenopausal women. Histological examination of the endometrium in 59.7% cases, HE is detected without atypia, polyps endometrium - in 22.4% of cases, atypical changes in the endometrium - in 1.4% of cases.

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